

Assessment of Family Socio-Economic Status, Availability of Instructional Facilities and Drop-Out of Basic Education Students in Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study assessed family socio-economic status and availability of instructional facilities on drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State. A Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population Basic Education students were 92,682, the sample size of 383 respondents participated in the study, purposive and random sampling techniques was used by the researchers. A questionnaire with the title: "Family socio-economic status and instructional facilities (F-SESIF) questionnaire" was developed. The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics; the mean and standard deviation were also used to answer the research questions. All and hypotheses were being tested using parametric statistic of One Sample t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The first finding indicated that there was no significant difference between family Socio-Economic status and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State and the second finding also revealed that there was no significant difference between availability of instructional facilities and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State. Based on the findings, it was therefore recommended that The Government should ensure that cost of education is reduced to the barest minimum and School Grown Feeding should be improved and extended to other levels of Basic Education. Also, government should encourage parents to send their children to school; parents who refuse to send their children to school should be punished as it is stated in the UBE Act.

Keywords: Drop-out, Basic Education, socio-economic status & instructional facilities

Introduction

Education is a fundamental right of every person, a key to other human rights, the heart of all developments, the prerequisite for equity, diversity and lasting peace. It is seen as a powerful means to reduce poverty and achieve economic growth. It empowers people, improves individuals' earning potential, promotes health population, is a major determinant of democracy and builds a competitive economy. Education as an organized and sustained instruction designed to communicate a combination of knowledge, skills and understanding valuable for all activities of life (UNESCO, 2000). This study will adopt the UNESCO definition because it talks about "organized and sustained instruction" which takes place informal education set-up. It has not always been possible that learners acquire necessary knowledge and skills as the definition of education demonstrates, because some of them drop-out of school. Drop-out phenomena as cases of children leaving school before completing the prescribed cycle of education. According to this definition, children may decide to leave school voluntarily or may be pushed out of the system by number of factors. Whichever the case, these problems result into waste in terms of inefficient utilization of both human and economic resources by the education system.

The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) has revealed that more than 3,3 million children drop out of basic schools in Nigeria because of poverty and other inhibiting factors. The Fund said that this poor retention and transition have significantly contributed to the out-of-school children phenomenon in the country. Nigeria is said to have over 10.2 million school age children that are not in school, with majority of them being are females, especially from the North. The education manager, UNICEF Field Office, Sokoto, Miriam Moreso, while speaking at a media dialogue on girls' education in Sokoto, stated that this was what prompted the implementation of the Girls Education Project (GEP3), funded by the United Kingdom Agency, Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Fund Office (FCDO), formerly known as DFID in six Northern states (Nigerian Tribune, 2022).

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The issue of school dropout in Nigeria especially Zamfara state has been with education system for a very long time. Fafunwa Kainuwa, Yusuf and Saibon (2017) noted that dropout is one of the most serious problems that have continued to affect our educational system negatively since independence in 1960 from the colonial administration. Even before we got our independence, the problem of dropout has already established its grip on our educational system. Dropping out from school occurs after children have previously achieved access to school. A major problem in many developing countries, dropping out is often obscured within statistical data and by the emphasis on initial access (Kainuwa et al, 2017). Dropping out of students from secondary schools can be caused by many factors such as parental and school factors.

Economic factors of parent which include monthly family income, financial situation during the past years, engaging in selling, accessing of internet connection, organizing extra lessons, cost of transportation and cost of text books are found to be some of the contributing factors to secondary school dropout (Kainuwa, 2014). Children from some of the Nigerian states are not likely to enrol in school, and if they do it is unlikely, they will complete primary and secondary education due to the high level of poverty. High levels of poverty often force parents to choose between food for the family and school for the children. This situation becomes magnified when looking at higher levels of education and contributes to the cycle of poverty passed on from generation to generation. Often parents choose to take their children out of school and involve them in activities that produce income, and many times these activities are illegal, immoral, and extremely detrimental to the lives of the children (National Bureau of Statistics, 2009; United Nations Millennium Goals, 2008). In Nigeria more especially in the study area, there is high poverty rate among parents which may be attributed to economic factors. This may have relationship with their inability to meet the financial demands for their children schooling (Yusuf in Kainuwa, et al, 2017).

Failure to complete Basic School Education not only limits future career opportunities for children but also represents a significant drain on the limited resources that countries have for the provision of Basic Education. Despite its importance, strategies designed to improve school retention and progression has received relatively little attention. Typically, national education plans assume that secondary school progression will improve automatically as a result of inventions designed to improve initial access and educational quality. Therefore, a study of this nature is pertinent and crucial as it is meant to raise awareness concerning school dropout and to understand more specifically the phenomenon of school dropout in Basic Education Schools, especially in Zamfara State and to provide strategies remedies for sustainable Basic Education school attendance and completion for those enrolled.

The major concern in basic education is ensuring that students stay in school until they complete their education. Dropping out is a serious problem because it denies individual students their fundamental human right to education. Internationally, the individual right to education has been repeatedly affirmed in many treaties and conventions such as the 1948 convention on the rights of the child and the 1990 World Conference on Education for All (UNESCO, 2000) of which Nigeria is one of the signatories. There is general consensus that the school drop-out problem has reached epidemic proportions internationally and has become a global problem confronting the education industry round the world (Wotherspoon, 2004; Bridge land, Entwisle and Horsey, 2006).

Family Economic status is contributing to the number of out of school children which have to do with socio-economic needs of the children and their families. These needs are rooted in the socio- economic status of people. This has far reaching implications on the demand for education of children in the family. Wealthy families can generally afford the education of their children, and prevent poverty inspired symptomatic activities and behaviour that impede children's access to education and retention in school till completion and graduation. But poor families cannot do likewise; their children are embattled by many economic related or poverty inspired constraints that often result in their failure to access basic education or dropping out from school after enrolment, without completion and graduation. Parental level of wealth or family's socio-economic status is a critical factor in demand for education, especially in countries such as Nigeria where though basic education is free, but sometimes encumbered by hidden costs. Children from poor families constitute most of the observed proportions of the un-enrolled and dropouts at all levels of basic education in Nigeria, (CASSAD, 2005, SITAN, 2007, Okeke, Nzewi and Njoku, 2008) in (UNICEF, 2012).

School related factors that cause out of school children: lack of school facilities and infrastructure, shortage of teachers or poor quality of teachers and teaching etc. are on the supply side of education. They can very severely influence children's access, retention, completion, and dropout rates from school, as well as other educational choices made by parents and guardians for their wards/children. Inadequate Implementation of Pre-primary Articulation Policy to public Primary Schools, many public primary schools especially in rural communities are yet to implement the policy on articulation of pre-primary sections to themselves, (SITAN, 2010), thereby making pre-primary schools inaccessible to majority of under-5 children. This is because most of the schools have no accommodation and no teachers or caregivers for the ECCD classes that would be

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added. The non-comprehensive implementation of this policy would definitely undermine the objective of bringing ECCD close to the people, especially in rural communities of Nigeria. Thus, pre-primary schools are still far from the pre-school children.

In Zamfara state, the primary level enrolment is projected to grow by an annual average of 4% per year, from roughly 474,000 in 2014 to 731,000 in 2025. In the Universal Basic Education sciences, it grows by an annual average of 9% to 1.2 million in 2005 (ZMSG, 2017). Moreover, JSS enrolment is projected to grow by an annual average of 4% in the status quo scenario and by 15% in the Universal Basic Education scenario. The relatively high growth rate of JSS enrolment in the latter scenario compared to primary enrolment reflects the fact that Gross Enrolment Rate (GERs) is higher at the primary level at baseline (ZMSG, 2017). Despite this trend and the increased severity of the negative consequences of dropping-out for many secondary schools, students particularly those from low-income families graduating from school has remained problematic (Hammond, 2007). Hence, this study assessed the family socio-economic status and availability of instructional facilities on Drop-out of Basic Education students in Zamfara State.

The term dropout is a word which has been defined by different researchers in different ways and to some extent it is an ambiguous concept. Dropout is an issue in educational systems that have aroused the interest of many professional academicians and the public in general. Dropout is often used in public schools to refer to those students that leave school without the school's consent either to another school or "sit" at home, a number of interpretations to the term have been attached (Mawere, 2012). Loxley (1985) define dropouts as "pupils who leave school before the final year of the educational cycle in which they are enrolled, which could be primary, ordinary or advanced level, or even college or university level". It is also important to put emphasis on the fact that pupils do not only leave school before completing a given educational cycle, but leave without the school's consent. Mawere (2012) stresses that it is the lack of consent that makes the school difficult to account for the pupil. This study therefore will refer to dropout as a pupil who leaves school before completing a given basic educational cycle and without the school's consent.

Also, according to Momo, Cabus, DeWitte and Groot (2018), it is a term used for the children, who for any reason other than death, discontinue schooling and leave their education uncompleted. This definition includes students at all levels of studies. Similarly, Malik (2002) defined dropout as a student who left school before completing a course of study. It is a comprehensive definition covering all students leaving their study incomplete. Similarly, Wegner, Flisher, Chikobvu, Lombard and King (2008) also defined dropout as children who quit school before completing the grade level they enrolled in for a given academic year. This implies that dropouts are children who were enrolled in school but have left school before completion as a result of individual, family, school, and community related problems. In contrast, Lewin and Little (2011) defined dropout as a pupil who starts education very late and who is prevented from completing owing to repetition. Considering all the above definitions, this study defined dropout operationally as a term which refers to a child who was once enrolled in school system but has left school for various reasons before the completion a certain grade level excluding those students who are repeaters and re-admitters in a certain grade level in the education system.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) states that Basic education shall be of 9 years duration, comprising 6 years of primary education and 3 years of junior secondary education. It shall also include adult and non-formal education programmes at primary and junior secondary education levels for the adults and out of school youths. Basic Education means the type of education given in the first level of education. The meaning of basic education changes from country to country. In Nigeria, basic education was equated with six years of primary schooling in the past. Currently basic education is extended to include the three years of Junior Secondary School. It embraces formal and non-formal education including education of the marginalized groups within the Nigerian society. The Programme is aimed at eradicating illiteracy, ignorance and poverty (UBE, 2011 in Bakwai, Yisa, & Jega, 2014).

Basic Education according to the National Policy on Education NPE (FRN, 2013) is the education given to the children aged 0-15 years. It encompasses the Early Child Care and Development Education (0-4) and 10 years of formal schooling which also includes 1 year of Pre-Primary, 6 years of Primary and 3 years of Junior Secondary Education. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013), stated that, the Basic Education, to be provided by Government, shall be compulsory, free, universal and qualitative. It comprises: 1- year of pre-Primary; 6 years of Primary; 3 years of Junior Secondary Education. Students'/pupils' enrolment is the total number of students/pupils registered in a specific level (class) in a particular year irrespective of gender age and school location (UNESCO, 2009). Students'/pupils' enrolment ratio refers to the total enrolment in a specific level of education, regardless of age and gender, which is expressed in percentage of the eligible official school age population corresponding to the same level of education in a given school year (Ongmsola, 2005). This study is based on Charles Darwins (1882) Classical Liberal Theory of Equal opportunity and socio Darwinism. The theory asserts that each person is born with a

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given amount of capacity, which to a large extent is inherent and cannot be substantially changed. Therefore, the education system should be designed so as to remove barriers of any nature such as economic, cultural, gender or geographical, in order to fully utilize their capacity. Orodho, (2005) cites liberal activists such as Horance Mann (1952), who termed education, as the great equalizers” Instrument which would enhance life chances.

Objectives of the Study

The study was guided by the following specific objectives, which are to:

1. assess family Socio-Economic status on level of drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State.
2. assess availability of instructional facilities on level drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State.

Research Questions

This research is designed to provide answers to the following research questions:

1. To what extent does level of family Socio-Economic status affect drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara state?
2. To what extent does the availability of instructional facilities affect drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State?

Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were formulated and tested to guide the study at 0.05 significant level:

1. There is no significant difference between family Socio-Economic status and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State;
2. There is no significant difference between availability of instructional facilities and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design following the recommendation of Dada (2016) who stated that descriptive survey research is a detailed study, which strives to explain or determine and report the way things are. It is the type of research that specifies the true nature of a given problem or event. The descriptive survey research further involves assessing situations through the administration of instruments that are specifically prepared for such a purpose. The choice of survey design for this research was based on the fact that the entire population cannot be covered, and so a sampling procedure would be done. The population of this study was drawn from all Junior Secondary Schools in fourteen (14) Local Government Areas in three (3) Senatorial Districts in Zamfara State. The population Basic Education students were ninety-two thousand, six hundred and eighty-two (92,682) (ZSMOE, 2022). The sample size of 383 respondents was participated in the study. This is based on the sample size selection table by Research Advisors (2006), which suggests that for a population of 75,001-100,000, a sample size of 383 is sufficient for generalization at 95% confidential level and 5% margin of error. Six (6) Local Government Areas and thirty-three (33) Basic Schools were purposively selected by the researchers, and simple random sampling technique was also used by the researchers (using hat and draw method) and select 383 basic education students who was the respondents of the study.

A questionnaire with the title: “Family socio-economic status and instructional facilities (F-SESIF) questionnaire” was developed. The questionnaire was in two parts- A and B. Part A obtain the respondents’ general information while Part B consisted of questions or statements in relation to the objectives of the study using four (4) points modified Likert measuring scale; such as, 4- SA (Strongly Agree), 3- A (Agree), 2- D (Disagree) and 1- SD (Strongly Disagree). After constructing the questionnaire, it is subjected to face, construct and content validity by specialists and experts in education from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Faculty of Education Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria validated in order to scrutinize the instruments, by checking items with the objectives and hypotheses of the study. The instrument was also pilot tested and the result was statistically analyzed for reliability co-efficient using Cronbach alpha at 0.05 level of significant. The reliability co-efficient of 0.81 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Based on this, the instrument was adjudged thus, the instrument is reliable and could be used for the study.

The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics; the mean and standard deviation were also used to answer the research questions. All and hypotheses were being tested using parametric statistic of One Sample t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Due to the fact that, one sample t-test statistical tool determines whether the sample mean is statistically different from unknown population mean (Jumare, 2017).

Results

Assessment of Family Socio-Economic Status ... (Hallilu, & Sani, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8381538>

Research Question 1

To what extent does level of family Socio-Economic status affect drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara state?

Table 1: Responses of the Respondents on how Family Socio-Economic status affects drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	M	StD
1.	Low parental occupational status influences students' drop-out from school in Zamfara State.	55	149	137	40	2.57	.86
2.	Low parental level of education is associated with increase high rate of students' drop-out from school in Zamfara State.	70	214	84	13	2.89	.73
3.	Low Parental level of income truncated the access of children to education due to cost of schooling in Zamfara State	104	207	60	10	3.06	.73
4.	Large family size limits the parental involvement in the academic welfare of each child lead to pupils'/students' drop-out from school in Zamfara State.	101	197	63	20	2.99	.80
5.	Children of divorced parents are more likely to have academic problems like anxiety, depression etc. leads to students' drop-out in Zamfara State.	81	190	91	19	2.87	.89
6.	Poverty as a factor affects children in both rural and some urban schools who had to walk long distance bare footed to school, which lead students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	85	194	84	18	2.90	.79
7.	Parents need for child labour /income generation activities e.g. gold mining leads to pupils' /students' drop-out in Zamfara State.	102	183	76	20	2.96	.82
8.	Inadequate schools' attendance by students in rainy season where students are to do farming leads to students' drop-out in Zamfara State.	90	176	97	18	2.89	.82
9.	Low level of parental income causes child hunger /malnutrition and illness influences students' drop-out of school in Zamfara	82	202	82	15	2.91	.76
10	Broken home destabilized children attention to learn effectively and leads to students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	80	175	90	36	2.79	.89
Cumulative Mean/STD						2.88	.81

Decision mean = 2.50

Note: M=Mean, StD=Standard Deviation, SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree

Table shows the result of the opinions of respondents on the level of family Socio-Economic status affects drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara state. According to the result which presented the mean and standard deviation for each item, majority of the respondents were in agreement with the all items, because all the mean of the items were above 2.50, also the cumulative mean was 2.88 which is above 2.50 as decision mean and this showed that the respondents were in agreement that family Socio-Economic status were among the causes of drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara state.

Research Question 2:

To what extent does the availability of instructional facilities affect drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State?

Assessment of Family Socio-Economic Status ... (Hallilu, & Sani, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8381538>

Table 2: Responses of the respondents on how instructional facilities affects drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	M	StD
11.	Inadequate well-ventilated class rooms may lead to students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	55	84	146	96	2.26	.98
12.	Unavailability of sanitation facilities e.g., toilet in schools massively leads to students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	22	49	262	48	2.13	.68
13.	Inadequate teaching/learning facilities e.g., chair, tables, text books etc. leads to students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	12	27	203	139	1.77	.71
14.	Poor and unpleasant school environment including not having pleasant playground leads to students drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	10	82	161	128	1.94	.82
15.	Unavailability of health facilities in the school leads to students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	11	47	237	86	1.96	.69
16.	Inadequate feeding by home growing feeding leads to students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	61`	86	172	62	2.38	.94
17.	Present of old and dilapidated structures in the schools which serve as a hiding place for dangerous animals, lead drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	24	100	167	90	2.15	.85
18.	Inadequate functional libraries, laboratories and computer centers influences students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State	14	127	163	77	2.20	.80
19.	Unavailability of security facilities like CCTV, security personnel led to students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	54	102	140	85	2.33	.97
20	Unavailability of portable drinking water in school influences students' drop-out of school in Zamfara State.	08	72	216	85	2.01	.70
Cumulative Mean/STD						2.11	82

Decision mean = 2.50

Note: M=Mean, StD=Standard Deviation, SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree

Table 2 shows the result of the opinions of respondents on the availability of instructional facilities affects drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State. According to the result which presented the mean and standard deviation for each item, respondents were not in agreement with the all items, because all the mean of the items were below 2.50, also the cumulative mean was 2.11 which is below 2.50 as decision mean and this showed that the respondents are not in agreement that non-availability of instructional facilities were not among the causes of drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between family Socio-Economic status and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State.

Table 3: One Sample t-test of the respondents on family Socio-Economic status and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State

Category	t	Test Value = 2.88			95% Confidence Interval of Difference	
		Df	Sig.	Mean Difference	Lower	Upper
		Family Socio-Economic Status	380	0.86	-.00287	-.0340

To determine if there is no significant difference between family Socio-Economic status and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State, one Sample t-test statistics was used on Table 3 above. It revealed that the statistic of (-.18), the number of degrees of freedom of (380), mean difference of (-.00287) and p-value of (0.86) was obtained, therefore, since the p-value of 0.86 is greater than alpha value of 0.05 (0.86 > 0.05), the null hypothesis which stated that there is no

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significant difference between family Socio-Economic status and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State was retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between availability of instructional facilities and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State.

Table 6: One Sample t-test on the opinions of the respondents on availability of instructional facilities and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State

Category	t	df	Test Value = 2.11		95% Confidence Interval of Difference	
			Sig.	Mean Difference	Lower	Upper
Availability of instructional facilities	.110	380	0.91	.00155	-.0261	.0292

To determine if there is no significant difference between availability of instructional facilities and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State, one Sample t-test statistics was used on Table 4 above. It revealed that the statistic of (.110), the number of degrees of freedom of (380), mean difference of (.00155) and p-value of (0.91) was obtained, therefore, since the p-value of 0.91 is greater than alpha value of 0.05(0.91 > 0.05), the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between availability of instructional facilities and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State was retained.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion is based on the variables contained in the study which were guided by the research questions and research hypotheses tested. The first finding indicated that there was no significant difference between family Socio-Economic status and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State. The study found that family Socio-Economic status were a significant cause of drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara state. This finding however, is in line with the finding of Kainuwa, Yusuf and Saibon (2017) in their study Relationship between Parental Economic Factors, and Students’ Dropouts from Government Secondary Schools of Zamfara, that the majority of secondary school dropouts come from households headed by low-income families; most parents of secondary school dropouts are engaged in low income generating occupations in the informal sector and earn or possess an insignificant amount of property. The dropping out of secondary school students in their study has generally been related to the low parental economic factors. This is particularly true for rural areas such as villages and less so in urban areas such as towns and cities. It is also in line with the outcome of Esayas (2019) who’s finding on the study on Prevalence, Causes and Prevention of Primary School Dropout in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia revealed that inability of the parents to cover basic educational expenses is found as one of the major causes of school dropout in the study area regardless of the free education policy that the country has lunched.

The second finding of the study revealed that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between availability of instructional facilities and drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State was retained. The study also concluded that non-availability of instructional facilities was not attributed as a cause of drop-out of basic education students in Zamfara State. This finding is opposed the finding of Thiruane (2016) in her study on the Investigating the Causes of Pupils Dropout in Public Primary Schools in Imenti North Sub County, Meru County, Kenya that availability of physical facilities such as classrooms, toilets, desks, water tanks and teaching aids are important in retaining children at school and therefore in the case that these facilities are not adequately provided then pupils can drop out of school.

Conclusion

The extent of school drop-out in Nigeria cannot be toyed with, especially in the present situation of economic hardship. Based on the findings of this study, several tendencies causing dropout rates were identified. Apparent that there is no specific cause of student drop-out behaviour rather it occurs for a wide range of reasons that interact with one another in a complex

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fashion. Also, based on the findings of this study it is therefore concluded that the dropping-out of basic school students in this study has been related to the family socio-economic status in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made to help in the effective curving of Dropping out from Basic Education in Zamfara State, Nigeria:

1. The Government should ensure that cost of education is reduced to the barest minimum and School Grown Feeding should be improved and extended to other levels of Basic Education. Also, government should encourage parents to send their children to school; parents who refuse to send their children to school should be punished as it is stated in the UBE Act; and
2. Stakeholders should ensure that Basic Schools are provided with adequate and qualitative infrastructures/facilities, the facilities needed are a good library, audio visual aids equipment(s), computers, play grounds etc. and this will enhance teaching and learning activities.

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